

MAPWORMS

Mimicking Adaptation
and Plasticity in
WORMS

D4.3 SYNTHESIS AND CHARACTERIZATION OF SHAPE- MEMORY AND SELF-HEALING HYDROGELS

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1 INTRODUCTION

The MAPWORMS project introduces a novel approach to robotic design, inspired by the remarkable adaptation and plasticity observed in marine worms, **Figure 1**. In particular, marine Annelida adapted to thrive across diverse environments, providing a rich biological model for shaping the next generation of soft, modular robots. Unlike conventional robotics, which often relies on centralized control and rigid structures, the MAPWORMS project draws inspiration from the distributed control strategies and elastic compliance found in marine worms. By leveraging advances in soft robotics and material science, the MAPWORMS project aims to develop robots capable of autonomous, safe operation in unstructured environments. Stimuli-responsive hydrogels, especially stiffness-switchable gel systems encoding structural and functional information, have been demonstrated. Within this framework, the project pursues the development of synthetic actuation units embedded in a smart, modular architecture, designed to reshape and adapt in response to environmental stimuli. The biomimetic workflow includes the detailed functional and morphological characterization of model marine worms, **Figure 1 A**, followed by the mathematical modelling of shape changes via localized modulation of rest and stiff states, **Figure 1 B**. Stimuli-responsive DNA-based hydrogels, capable of cyclic, controlled stiffness transitions, are being developed as responsive morphing materials, **Figure 1 C**. Finally, these smart materials will be integrated as functional elements and building blocks for realizing stimuli-responsive, shape-morphing devices, mimicking adaptation and plasticity observed in marine worms, giving rise to reconfigurable robotic structures with self-adaptive capabilities across different size scales, **Figure 1 D**. Through this integrated approach, MAPWORMS aims to bridge biological insight, material innovation, and robotic engineering to highlight new frontiers in soft, adaptive robotics.

Figure 1. Biomimetic workflow of the MAPWORMS project. A. Biological and structural characterization of selected marine worms. B. Mathematical modelling of the characterized worms. C. Soft “smart” actuating hydrogel materials design. D. Assembly of a biomimetic worm robot.

Thus, an important goal of the project involves the “**Synthesis and characterization of shape-memory and self-healing hydrogels**”. The present report addresses achievements during the initial 36 months

of the project in developing methods to fabricate stimuli-responsive shape-memory and self-healing hydrogels. In addition, future perspectives and challenges are addressed.

2 REDOX-RESPONSIVE TRANSIENT, DISSIPATIVE, STIFFNESS-CONTROLLED GELS FOR SHAPE MEMORY, SELF-HEALING, BENDING ACTUATIONS, AND CONTROLLED RELEASE OF LOADS

In the previous reports, we addressed the preparation of transient, dissipative, stimuli-responsive cryostructured gels and their applications for controlled load-release and dynamic robotic morphing through bending actuation. The gels consisted of $\text{Fe}^{3+}/\text{Fe}^{2+}$ -ion crosslinked carboxymethyl cellulose (CMC), triggered by chemical or light stimuli. This scientific effort has been published ^[1] in an open-access paper, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **146**, 9957–9966, 2024,^[1] acknowledging the MAPWORMS European project, 101046846. These cryostructured gels suffer, however, from several limitations, including: (i) The framework includes only one crosslinking element (carboxylate- $\text{Fe}^{3+}/\text{Fe}^{2+}$ -ion) that is stimuli-responsive, thus preventing its development for shape-memory applications; (ii) The framework was assembled only as a cryostructured gel and could not be formed as a hydrogel formulation; (iii) The light-responsive system employed auxiliary, diffusional components (photosensitizer). For any practical application, integration of the photosensitizer into the gel framework is essential.

The research activities within the present reporting period address these issues by developing new hydrogel/cryogel frameworks, revealing superior properties, aiming to resolve the stated difficulties and limitations. The accomplishments achieved within the reporting period and the plan for further developments are discussed.

2.1 METHOD TO FABRICATE THE COOPERATIVELY-CROSSLINKED REDOX-RESPONSIVE DISSIPATIVE GELS

A new class of hydrogel/cryogel frameworks consisting of methacrylated carboxymethyl cellulose (CMC-MA) units was developed, **Figure 2**. The method to synthesize the cooperatively-crosslinked redox-responsive dissipative gels involves redox-initiated covalent crosslinking through the acrylate groups, followed by carboxylate- Fe^{3+} redox-responsive crosslinking.

Figure 2. Schematic preparation of redox-responsive Fe^{3+/2+}-crosslinked CMC-MA and control over the gel stiffness.

It is important to notice that the gel includes interchain covalent crosslinking methacrylate bridges serving as “memory” elements, and carboxylate-Fe³⁺/Fe²⁺-ions motifs as redox-responsive crosslinking units.

2.2 REDOX-RESPONSIVE TRANSIENT, DISSIPATIVE STIFFNESS PROPERTIES OF THE GEL AND ITS APPLICATIONS

2.2.1 REDOX-INDUCED, TRANSIENT, DISSIPATIVE CONTROL OVER THE GEL MATRICES STIFFNESS PROPERTIES

The gel frameworks demonstrated transient, dissipative stiffness properties. The transient stiffness of the gel matrices was characterized by rheometry, **Figure 3**. Moreover, by loading the gel matrix with Ru[TRP]²⁺ (photosensitizer) in the presence of MES buffer as a sacrificial electron donor, control over the stiffness properties of the gel was demonstrated.

- The stimuli-responsive ascorbate-induced transition of the Fe³⁺-CMC-MA to the Fe²⁺-CMC-MA frameworks, and the autonomous, dissipative recovery of the gel to the high-stiffness state (Fe³⁺-CMC-MA) is exemplified, **Figure 3 A**.

- The stimuli-responsive light-induced transition of the Fe^{3+} -CMC-MA to the Fe^{2+} -CMC-MA frameworks, and the autonomous, dissipative recovery of the gel to the high-stiffness state (Fe^{3+} -CMC-MA) is exemplified, **Figure 3 B**.
- The transient behaviour of the light-induced stiffness changes is controlled by the dose of Fe^{3+} -crosslinking the gel matrices.

Figure 3. Rheometry characterization of: A. Ascorbate-induced reduction of Fe^{3+} -CMC-MA to Fe^{2+} -CMC-MA under air. B. Light-induced reduction of Fe^{3+} -CMC-MA to Fe^{2+} -CMC-MA under air.

2.2.2 APPLICATION OF THE DISSIPATIVE STIFFNESS PROPERTIES TOWARD DISSIPATIVE SELF-HEALING MATRICES

- A cooperatively-crosslinked $\text{Fe}^{3+/2+}$ -CMC-MA hydrogel framework was employed as a self-healing matrix, **Figure 4**. In these experiments, high-stiffness square-shaped Fe^{3+} -CMC-MA matrices were reduced by ascorbate to yield the low-stiffness state Fe^{2+} -CMC-MA. These gels were cut into two pieces and then physically interjoined under air or nitrogen. The physical interconnection of two gel pieces of low-stiffness leads, upon O_2 -mediated oxidation of Fe^{2+} to Fe^{3+} , to the regeneration of Fe^{3+} -CMC-MA at the two pieces interface, resulting in a self-healed, high-stiffness gel. The samples under air underwent O_2 -mediated transient oxidation and recovery to the Fe^{3+} -CMC-MA high-stiffness gel state, resulting in a self-healed junction and framework consisting of the high-stiffness gel matrices, **Figure 4 A**.
- In contrast to the samples under air, the samples under nitrogen did not undergo the transient transition to the high-stiffness state, eliminating the self-healing process, **Figure 4 B**.

Figure 4. Self-healing process of: A. Fe³⁺-CMC-MA cryogel under air. B. Fe³⁺-CMC-MA cryogel under N₂.

Accordingly, the results demonstrated the self-healing application of the redox-responsive Fe³⁺/Fe²⁺-CMC-MA gel frameworks.

2.2.3 APPLICATION OF THE DISSIPATIVE STIFFNESS PROPERTIES TOWARD CONTROLLED, TRANSIENT RELEASE OF LOADS

Fe^{3+/2+}-CMC-MA cryogel frameworks were prepared in the presence of carbon-dots (C-dots) as a load. The light-induced transient release in the presence of Ru[TRP]²⁺ as a diffusional photosensitizer was examined. The release of the load from the gel matrices was evaluated by probing the fluorescence of the C-dots in the bulk solution ($\lambda_{ex}=350\text{ nm}$, $\lambda_{em}=430\text{ nm}$). The results are displayed in

Figure 5.

- Photoinduced transformation of the gel from high-stiffness Fe³⁺-CMC-MA to the low-stiffness state Fe²⁺-CMC-MA triggers “on” the release of the C-dots, and the transient O₂-mediated recovery of the Fe²⁺-CMC-MA to the Fe³⁺-CMC-MA state, leads to the temporal high-stiffness gel, which slows down the release, leading upon complete conversion of the Fe²⁺-CMC-MA to the Fe³⁺-CMC-MA, where the release is blocked (“off”), **Figure 5 A**.
- The dynamic release patterns of the load were controlled by the dose of irradiation. The longer the irradiation time interval, the higher the initial dose of load-release, consistent with the higher degree of stiffness decrease upon longer illumination time intervals, **Figure 5 B**.

Figure 1. Light-induced reduction of Fe³⁺-CMC-MA to Fe²⁺-CMC-MA under air for controlled load-release. A. Light-induced time-dependent load-release. B. Time-dependent rate of load-release.

In conclusion, these experiments demonstrated the load-release application of the redox-responsive Fe^{3+/2+}-CMC-MA gel frameworks.

2.2.4 APPLICATION OF THE DISSIPATIVE STIFFNESS PROPERTIES TOWARD TRANSIENT, DISSIPATIVE SHAPE-MEMORY MATRICES

The previous results we reported described the preparation of a transient, dissipative Fe^{3+/2+}-CMC cryogel demonstrating transient load-release capacities, and the possible application of the cryogel for robotic, transient bending in a bi-layer gel configuration. Nevertheless, this Fe^{3+/2+}-CMC transient cryogel framework suffered from basic limitations in the adaptive application as a shape-memory matrix. The lack of a permanent “memory” element in the framework prohibited the instructive dynamic recovery of a low-stiffness shapeless gel configuration into the parent structurally defined framework. The newly synthesized Fe^{3+/2+}-CMC-MA gel framework resolves, however, this limitation. The methacrylate crosslinking of the polymer chains provides an internal, permanent, “memory” element complementary to the redox-responsive Fe^{3+/2+}-carboxylate crosslinking elements, thus allowing, in principle, the control over the stiffness of the gel, retaining an internal “memory” to restore the pre-designed structure.

Toward the aim of transient, dissipative shape-memory matrices, CMC-MA polymers were chemically crosslinked in a triangle mold, followed by incubation with Fe²⁺-ions and their subsequent O₂-mediated oxidation to obtain a high-stiffness hydrogel in the shape of the triangle mold, **Figure 6 A**. Treatment of the high-stiffness triangle-shaped hydrogel with ascorbate lead to the transition of the high-stiffness Fe³⁺-CMC state to the low-stiffness Fe²⁺-CMC state, and the accompanied loss of the

triangle shape. Yet, the permanent covalent crosslinking motifs acted as “memory”, guiding the restoration of the high-stiffness Fe^{3+} -CMC triangle-shaped hydrogel, **Figure 6 B**.

Figure 2. A. Schematic assembly of a triangle-shaped Fe^{3+} -CMC-MA for shape-memory application. B. Ascorbate-induced reduction of Fe^{3+} -CMC-MA to Fe^{2+} -CMC-MA under air for 20 hours.

2.2.5 ASSEMBLY OF AN INTEGRATED PHOTOSENSITIZER GEL MATRIX AND ITS APPLICATIONS

A major breakthrough was achieved for light-controlled, transient, dissipative stiffness changes of the gel matrices through the integration of non-diffusive photosensitizer/redox-active gel matrices, **Figure 7**. In these experiments, photosystem I (PSI) operating in the natural photosynthetic apparatus was extracted from native sources. PSI, being a protein complex, was immobilized in a non-leakable configuration during the synthesis of the gels.

- The integrated PSI-gel matrices enabled the light-induced PSI-triggered electron transfer to the Fe^{3+} -carboxylate units, resulting in the transition of the high-stiffness Fe^{3+} -CMC-MA to the low-stiffness Fe^{2+} -CMC-MA, and the transient “dark” O_2 -mediated recovery of the gel matrix to the high-stiffness state Fe^{3+} -CMC-MA, **Figure 7 A**.
- The light-stimulated transient stiffness changes of the gels were characterized by rheometry, **Figure 7 B**.

- The light-stimulated self-healing functions of the PSI-loaded gel frameworks are now being characterized.
- The light-triggered load-release (dextran-functionalized tetramethyl rhodamine, TMR-D) was highlighted and is now being examined.
- Future goals include the application of the light-responsive integrated system for transient, dissipative, shape-morphing and robotic bending of bilayer gel structures.

Figure 3. A. Schematic assembly of a light-responsive photosystem-I-loaded Fe^{3+} -CMC-MA. B. Rheometry characterization of light-induced reduction of Fe^{3+} -CMC-MA to Fe^{2+} -CMC-MA under air and the accompanying stiffness changes.

Beyond the demonstration of photosensitizer integration in the gel frameworks, the environmentally sustainable features of the PSI gel system should be noted, for any future applications (biomedical, food packaging, etc).

3 SUMMARY AND FUTURE PERSPECTIVES

A summary of the importance of current research results and future efforts, and the relevance of the research to the MAPWORMS project, is provided:

HUJI developed novel methods to assemble redox-responsive, transient, dissipative stiffness gel frameworks composed of cooperatively crosslinked $\text{Fe}^{3+/2+}$ -CMC-MA. The important conclusions of the study include:

- (i) The introduction and characterization of a new class of redox-active transient, dissipative stiffness gel frameworks were accomplished. The gel stiffness was temporarily controlled by a chemical reducing agent (ascorbate) or by light.
- (ii) The self-healing properties of the transient $\text{Fe}^{3+/2+}$ -CMC-MA gel frameworks were demonstrated.
- (iii) The shape-memory properties of the transient $\text{Fe}^{3+/2+}$ -CMC-MA gel frameworks were demonstrated.
- (iv) The transient ascorbate/light-responsive stiffness changes of the gels were employed to design transiently-operating controlled load-release matrices.
- (v) Integrated light-responsive gel frameworks consisting of PSI were introduced. The PSI-integrated system demonstrated light-induced control over the temporal stiffness properties.

3.2 FUTURE PERSPECTIVES

The achievements described so far guide us toward the following future experiments:

1. The transient temporal stiffness changes of the $\text{Fe}^{3+/2+}$ -CMC-MA, characterized by rheometry and the self-healing features, will be complemented by temporarily probing the extension and compression features of the respective gels. Toward this goal, we used gel molds to produce “dog-bone”-shaped gel matrices, **Figure 8 A**. These gels will be examined for their stretching forces and breaking points at high-stiffness and low-stiffness states. Furthermore, the dissipative properties will be probed by following the temporal recovery of the stretching forces and their temporal breaking points.
2. The transient temporal self-healing properties will be examined through the stretching of non-healed and temporarily self-healed gel samples in different time intervals. The extension forces of the different gel states and the breaking point of the self-healed samples will be quantitatively measured, as depicted in **Figure 8 B**.

MA. These new gels demonstrated effective control over the redox-responsive transient stiffness properties. The redox responsiveness was stimulated by a chemical agent, ascorbate, and most importantly, by the integration of the photosynthetic reaction system, photosystem I, as an environmentally sustainable light-activating stimulus. These new stimuli-responsive cryogel/hydrogel matrices demonstrated effective self-healing properties, shape-memory, and controlled transient load-release functions, key deliverables of WP4. Moreover, the results introduced appropriate bridges to link the stimuli-responsive adaptivity of this synthetic framework with the adaptive soft behavior of native marine worms. This will allow us to formulate a comprehensive experimental and theoretical framework of results that integrates the activities of WP2 and WP3 with WP4 into a comprehensive interlinked study.

Based on the present results, we anticipate formulating in the next 2-3 months, two scientific reports describing: (i) the synthesis and characterization of the $\text{Fe}^{3+/2+}$ -CMC-MA framework, and its application as a functional matrix for self-healing, transient shape-memory, controlled load-release, and dynamic shape-morphing for robotic bending. (ii) The integration of the PSI into the $\text{Fe}^{3+/2+}$ -CMC-MA framework, the light-stimulated transient stiffness properties of the resulting gel, and its application for light-stimulated self-healing, shape-memory, controlled transient load-release, and shape-morphing for robotic applications. In addition, we plan to formulate a collaborative research paper, summarizing the experimental dynamic functions of the $\text{Fe}^{3+/2+}$ -CMC-MA framework, and their akin to the soft marine worms.

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